

PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF *COLEUS AROMATICUS* EXTRACT AND EVALUATING IT ACTIVITY AGAINST ETHANOL-INDUCED GASTRIC ULCER

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Abstract

Gastric ulcer is a common gastrointestinal disorder caused by an imbalance between aggressive factors such as gastric acid, ethanol, and pepsin, and defensive mechanisms of the gastric mucosa. Medicinal plants rich in bioactive phytochemicals have gained significant attention due to their gastroprotective potential and minimal side effects. The present study aimed to investigate the phytochemical constituents and anti-ulcer activity of the ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus* leaves using an ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model in rats. The leaves of *C. aromaticus* were subjected to ethanolic extraction, and the percentage yield was determined. Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed to identify the presence of bioactive constituents. Total phenolic and total flavonoid contents were quantitatively estimated. The anti-ulcer activity was evaluated in Wistar rats by assessing ulcer index, gastric pH, total acidity, free acidity, and pepsin activity following ethanol-induced gastric ulceration. Ranitidine was used as the standard drug. Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test. The ethanolic extract showed a percentage yield of 13.5% w/w and was found to contain flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, saponins, diterpenes, carbohydrates, and proteins. Quantitative analysis revealed appreciable levels of total phenolic and flavonoid content. Pretreatment with the ethanolic extract at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg significantly reduced the ulcer index and pepsin activity, while increasing gastric pH and decreasing total and free acidity compared to the control group. The gastroprotective effect was comparable to the standard drug ranitidine. The results suggest that the ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus* possesses significant anti-ulcer activity, which may be attributed to its antioxidant, anti-secretory, and cytoprotective properties mediated by bioactive phytoconstituents.

Keywords: *Coleus aromaticus*, Ethanolic extract, Phytochemical screening, Gastric ulcer, Ethanol-induced ulcer, Anti-ulcer activity; Ranitidine.

Introduction

Gastric ulceration is a common gastrointestinal disorder characterized by a breach in the mucosal layer of the stomach, resulting from an imbalance between aggressive factors (e.g., gastric acid, ethanol, *Helicobacter pylori*) and protective mechanisms such as mucus secretion, antioxidant defense, and mucosal blood flow (Erfan et al., 2025). Ethanol-induced gastric ulcer models are widely used in experimental pharmacology because ethanol disrupts the gastric mucosal barrier, reduces mucus secretion, increases oxidative stress, and causes inflammation, leading to erosions and ulcerations in the gastric lining. This model mimics acute mucosal injury and allows assessment of cytoprotective and antioxidant effects of therapeutic agents, especially herbal extracts with bioactive phytochemicals (Jaccob; 2025).

Medicinal plants are a rich source of bioactive secondary metabolites such as phenolics, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, and essential oils, which possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytoprotective properties that may contribute to gastroprotective effects against experimentally induced ulcers. These phytochemicals can scavenge free radicals, enhance mucosal defense mechanisms, inhibit lipid peroxidation, and modulate gastric secretions, thereby mitigating gastric mucosal damage (Bhatti et al., 2022).

Coleus aromaticus Benth., also known as *Plectranthus amboinicus* (Lour.) Spreng. (family Lamiaceae), is a perennial aromatic herb widely used in traditional medicine across tropical and subtropical regions to treat respiratory ailments, skin diseases, digestive disorders, fever, and inflammation. Phytochemical investigations have revealed that this species is rich in phenolic acids (e.g., rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid), flavonoids, terpenoids (e.g., carvacrol, linalool), and other volatiles, which contribute to its broad pharmacological profile including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities (Arumugam et al., 2016).

Several in vivo and in vitro studies have demonstrated the therapeutic potential of *P. amboinicus* extracts. For example, ethanolic extracts of the leaves exhibited significant antioxidant and cytotoxic activities, linked to high phenolic and flavonoid content, and high levels of bioactive volatiles such as carvacrol. Although research on *P. amboinicus* has focused on metabolic, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory effects, there is limited but growing evidence that crude extracts of this plant may offer gastroprotective activity in ulcer models. Traditional and

preliminary pharmacological reports have highlighted anti-ulcerogenic effects of *P. amboinicus* in rat models, suggesting that its phytochemicals could mitigate gastric mucosal injury when challenged with ulcerogenic agents.

Despite such promising findings, systematic studies on the ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model are scarce. Ethanol-induced ulceration is a relevant preclinical model to evaluate the gastroprotective potential of herbal extracts because it directly induces oxidative stress and mucosal disruption (Zhou et al., 2020). By studying this model, researchers can better understand the preventive and therapeutic effects of *C. aromaticus* extract, and correlate its phytochemical composition with anti-ulcer activity, potentially identifying active constituents responsible for gastroprotection.

Thus, this study aims to investigate the phytochemical profile of the ethanol extract of *Coleus aromaticus* and to evaluate its gastroprotective activity in the ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model in experimental animals, providing insights into its mechanism of action and therapeutic promise as a plant-based anti-ulcer agent.

Material and Methods

Material

Fresh leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* were collected and authenticated by a qualified botanist. Ethanol (analytical grade) was used for the preparation of the plant extract. Ranitidine was used as the standard anti-ulcer drug. Absolute ethanol was employed for the induction of gastric ulcers in experimental animals. Chemicals and reagents required for phytochemical screening, estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid content, and biochemical analysis of gastric parameters were of analytical grade and procured from standard commercial suppliers. Wistar albino rats were used for the evaluation of anti-ulcer activity.

Methods

Extraction procedure

Following procedure was adopted for the preparation of extract from the shade dried and powdered herbs (Khandelwal, 2005; Kokate, 1994):

Defatting of plant materials

Leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* was shade dried at room temperature. 50 gram shade dried plant material was coarsely powdered and subjected to extraction with petroleum ether by maceration method. The extraction was continued till the defatting of the material had taken place.

Extraction by maceration method

Defatted dried powdered leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* has been extracted with ethanol solvent using maceration process for 24-48 hrs, filtered and dried using vacuum evaporator at 40°C (Mukherjee, 2007).

Determination of percentage yield

The percentage yield of each extract was calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Extract}}{\text{Weight of powder drug Taken}} \times 100$$

Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemical tests are conducted to identify and determine the quantity of specific phytochemical compounds present in a plant extract or plant material. These tests employ various chemical, chromatographic, and spectroscopic techniques to isolate, separate, and characterize the phytochemicals. The choice of tests depends on the nature of the phytochemical of interest and the available resources. Phytochemical examinations were carried out for all the extracts as per the standard methods (Pradhan *et al.*, 2019).

Quantitative estimation of bioactive compound

Estimation of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by the modified folin-ciocalteu method (Parkhe and Bharti, 2019).

Preparation of Standard: 10 mg Gallic acid was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, various aliquots of 5- 25µg/ml was prepared in methanol.

Preparation of Extract: 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Two ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of phenol.

Procedure: 2 ml of each extract or standard was mixed with 1 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted with distilled water 1:10 v/v) and 1 ml (7.5g/l) of sodium carbonate. The mixture was vortexed for 15s and allowed to stand for 15 min for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a spectrophotometer.

Estimation of total flavonoids content

Determination of total flavonoids content was based on aluminium chloride method (Gaur Mishra *et al.*, 2017).

Preparation of standard: 10 mg quercetin was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, and various aliquots of 5- 25µg/ml were prepared in methanol.

Preparation of extract: 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Three ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of flavonoid.

Procedure: 1 ml of 2% AlCl₃ methanolic solution was added to 3 ml of extract or standard and allowed to stand for 15 min at room temperature; absorbance was measured at 420 nm.

In vivo* antiulcer activity of ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus

Animals

Wistar rats (150–200 g) were group housed (n= 6) under a standard 12 h light/dark cycle and controlled conditions of temperature and humidity (25±2 °C, 55–65%). Rats received standard rodent chow and water *ad libitum*. Rats were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for 7 days before carrying out the experiments. All the experiments were carried in a noise-free room between 08.00 to 15.00 h. Separate group (n=6) of rats was used for each set of experiments. The animal studies were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC), constituted for the purpose of control and supervision of experimental animals by Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India, New Delhi, India.

Toxicity study

Healthy adult male albino rats were fasted overnight prior to the experiment. Different doses (50-2000 mg/kg, P.O) of the ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* were administered to each group of rats (Each group carries 6 rats) and they were observed continuously for 1 hour

and then at half-hourly intervals for 4 hour, for any gross behavioural changes and further up to 72 hour, followed 14 days for any mortality as per the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) Guideline 425 (OECD, 2008). The ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* was found to be non-toxic up to the maximum dose of 2000 mg/kg body weight. Dose selected for antiulcer evaluation was 100 and 200 mg/kg respectively.

Experimental designs

Ulcer induced by absolute ethanol

The rats were divided into four groups of six each.

Group I (toxicant control) received absolute ethanol (1 ml/animal)

Group II was treated with ranitidine (50 mg/kg)

Groups III was treated with ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* 100 mg/kg/p.o.

Groups IV was treated with ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* 200 mg/kg/p.o.

The animals were treated with ranitidine (100 mg/kg), dose of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* 100 and 200 mg/kg (once daily) for 5 days after the induction of ulcer, while the control group received only the vehicle. The rats were fasted for 24 h and they received 1 ml of absolute ethanol orally. The animals were sacrificed after 1 h of ulcerogen administration, and their stomachs were excised and the gastric contents were aspirated. The contents were subjected to centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 10 min and then analyzed for pH (digital pH meter), pepsin activity, total and free acidity.

Antiulcer Screening

The ulcer index was determined using the formula (Mousa *et al.*, 2019):

$$\text{Ulcer index} = 10/X$$

Where X = Total mucosal area/Total ulcerated area.

Based on their intensity, the ulcers were given scores as follows:

0 = no ulcer, 1 = superficial mucosal erosion, 2 = deep ulcer or transmural necrosis,

3 = perforated or penetrated ulcer.

Results and Discussion

The present study was carried out to investigate the phytochemical profile and gastroprotective activity of the ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus* leaves using an ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model in rats. Ethanol is a potent ulcerogenic agent known to cause gastric mucosal injury through oxidative stress, increased gastric acid secretion, depletion of mucus, and impairment of gastric microcirculation. The marked gastric lesions observed in the control group confirm the suitability of the experimental model for evaluating anti-ulcer activity (Table 4).

The ethanolic extraction of *C. aromaticus* leaves produced a yield of 13.5% w/w, indicating effective extraction of polar and moderately polar phytoconstituents (Table 1). Preliminary phytochemical screening of the extract revealed the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, saponins, diterpenes, proteins, and carbohydrates, while alkaloids and glycosides were absent (Table 2). The presence of these bioactive constituents is pharmacologically significant, as many of them are reported to possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytoprotective properties that contribute to gastric mucosal protection.

Quantitative estimation demonstrated appreciable levels of total phenolic and total flavonoid content in the ethanolic extract (Table 3). Phenolic compounds and flavonoids are known to play a crucial role in gastroprotection by scavenging free radicals generated during ethanol-induced oxidative stress. These compounds also enhance prostaglandin synthesis, stimulate mucus secretion, and strengthen the gastric mucosal barrier, thereby reducing ulcer formation. The presence of tannins further supports gastroprotective activity by forming a protective layer over the gastric mucosa and preventing chemical and enzymatic injury.

Administration of ethanol resulted in a significant increase in ulcer index in the control group, indicating severe gastric mucosal damage (Table 4). Pretreatment with the ethanolic extract of *C. aromaticus* at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg significantly reduced the ulcer index when compared to the control group. Notably, the lower dose produced a greater reduction in ulcer index than the higher dose, suggesting that the gastroprotective effect may be influenced by optimal concentrations of phytoconstituents rather than a strictly dose-dependent response. The standard drug ranitidine also significantly reduced the ulcer index, validating the protective effects observed with the plant extract.

Ethanol administration caused a marked decrease in gastric pH, along with an increase in both total acidity and free acidity, reflecting excessive acid secretion and mucosal injury (Tables 5, 6, and 7). Pretreatment with the ethanolic extract significantly increased gastric pH and reduced total and free acidity in a dose-dependent manner. The reduction in gastric acidity suggests an anti-secretory effect of the extract, which may be attributed to inhibition of acid secretion or enhancement of mucosal defense mechanisms. Flavonoids and phenolic compounds are known to suppress histamine release, inhibit proton pump activity, and enhance mucus and bicarbonate secretion, thereby contributing to reduced gastric acidity.

Pepsin activity was significantly elevated in ethanol-treated animals, which further aggravates gastric mucosal damage by degrading mucosal proteins (Table 8). Pretreatment with the ethanolic extract significantly reduced pepsin activity, particularly at the higher dose, demonstrating its ability to suppress proteolytic enzyme activity. This effect may be attributed to the presence of tannins and flavonoids, which are known to inhibit digestive enzymes and stabilize the gastric mucosal barrier.

The gastroprotective effect of the ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus* leaves can be attributed to a multifactorial mechanism involving antioxidant, anti-secretory, and cytoprotective actions. The presence of bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, and saponins plays a vital role in protecting the gastric mucosa against ethanol-induced injury. These findings support the traditional use of *C. aromaticus* in the management of gastric disorders and highlight its potential as a natural anti-ulcer agent.

Table 1: % Yield of leaves extract of *Coleus aromaticus*

S. No.	Extract	% Yield (w/w)
1.	Ethanolic	13.5

Table 2: Phytochemical screening of extract of *Coleus aromaticus*

S. No.	Constituents	Ethanolic extract	Observation
1.	Alkaloids Mayer's Test: Wagner's Test: Dragendroff's Test: Hager's Test:	-ve -ve -ve -ve	Green coloured Green coloured Light Green coloured Yellow coloured
2.	Glycosides Legal's test	-ve	Green coloured

3.	Flavonoids Lead acetate Alkaline Reagent Test:	+ve -ve	Yellow coloured precipitate Yellow coloured
4.	Phenolics Ferric Chloride Test	+ve	Black coloured
5.	Proteins Xanthoproteic test	+ve	Yellow coloured
6.	Carbohydrates Molisch's Test: Benedict's Test: Fehling's Test:	-ve -ve +ve	Yellow coloured Yellow coloured Red precipitate
7.	Saponins Froth Test: Foam Test:	+ve -ve	Layer of foam No foam
8.	Diterpins Copper acetate test	+ve	Green coloured
9.	Tannins Gelatin Test:	+ve	White precipitate

Table 3: Total phenolic and total flavonoid content of *Coleus aromaticus*

S. No.	Total Phenol content	Total flavonoid content
	mg/100mg	
1.	0.526	1.074

Table 4: Effect of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* on ulcer index by ethanol induced ulcers in rats

Treatment and Dose	Ulcer Index (Mean \pm SEM)
Control	7.45 \pm 0.42
Ranitidine (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	4.25 \pm 0.12***
Ethanolic extract of <i>Coleus aromaticus</i> (100 mg/kg, p.o.)	3.05 \pm 0.20***
Ethanolic extract of <i>Coleus aromaticus</i> (200 mg/kg, p.o.)	3.82 \pm 0.25**

Table 5: Effect of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* on gastric parameters i.e. pH by ethanol-induced ulceration in rats

Treatment and Dose	Gastric pH (Mean \pm SEM)
Control	2.80 \pm 0.28
Ranitidine (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	4.70 \pm 0.18***
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (100 mg/kg, p.o.)	3.92 \pm 0.22**
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (200 mg/kg, p.o.)	4.25 \pm 0.17***

Table 6: Effect of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* on gastric parameters i.e. total acidity ethanol- induced ulceration in rats

Treatment and Dose	Total Acidity (mEq/L, Mean \pm SEM)
Control	74.85 \pm 0.35
Ranitidine (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	45.25 \pm 0.25***
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (100 mg/kg, p.o.)	61.10 \pm 0.28*
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (200 mg/kg, p.o.)	49.05 \pm 0.32***

Table 7: Effect of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* on gastric parameters i.e. free acidity by ethanol-induced ulceration in rats

Treatment and Dose	Free Acidity (mEq/L)
Control	59.95 \pm 0.35
Ranitidine (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	25.40 \pm 0.20 ***
Ethanolic extract of <i>Coleus aromaticus</i> (100 mg/kg, p.o.)	39.75 \pm 0.30 **
Ethanolic extract of <i>Coleus aromaticus</i> (200 mg/kg, p.o.)	36.80 \pm 0.35 ***

Table 8: Effect of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* on gastric parameters i.e. pepsin activity by ethanol-induced ulceration in rats

Treatment and dose	Pepsin activity (Per ml/h)
Control	3.28 \pm 0.22
Ranitidine (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	2.42 \pm 0.18 ***
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (100 mg/kg, p.o.)	3.38 \pm 0.28 **
Ethanolic extract of <i>C. aromaticus</i> (200 mg/kg, p.o.)	2.72 \pm 0.26 ***

Values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. (n = 6). Values are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ vs. control group respectively (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test).

Conclusion

The ethanolic extract of *Coleus aromaticus* leaves exhibited significant anti-ulcer activity against ethanol-induced gastric ulcers in rats. The gastroprotective effect may be attributed to the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which reduced ulcer index, gastric acidity, and pepsin activity while increasing gastric pH. These findings support the traditional use of *Coleus aromaticus* as a natural anti-ulcer agent.

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